

1168 cM with an average interval length of 9 cM.

Lengths of shoot, root, coleoptile, and mesocotyl were scored on 172 F₃ families in LBL/BG using replicated slantboard tests at two temperatures (18 and 25 °C) and on 113 F₃ families in LBL/IL at 18 °C. The slantboard test (Jones and Peterson 1976) is a standard laboratory procedure used for screening seedling vigor in California. Interval mapping (LOD = 2.5) using Mapmaker and single-point analyses (P < 0.05) using SAS programs (SAS Institute, 1989) identified 13 QTLs in LBL/BG, including four for shoot length, two each for root and coleoptile lengths, and five for mesocotyl length (see table). Three of these QTLs were expressed at both screening temperatures. In LBL/IL, 12 QTLs were identified including two for coleoptile length and five each for root and mesocotyl lengths (see table).

Most QTLs, including those detected from the common maternal parent, mapped to different rice chromosomes in the two crosses. These results suggest that both genetic background and screening environment may influence QTL expression for seedling vigor. Different sets

of alleles conferring increased seedling vigor may be present in high-vigor indica and japonica genetic donors. The indica BG contributed QTLs with only minor effects for shoot length, the most important determinant of seedling vigor in California's water-seeded rice culture. However, an allele from the temperate japonica cultivar IL accounting for 18.5% of the shoot length variation was identified by single-point analysis. Positive alleles at QTLs identified in the two populations may be useful for seedling vigor enhancement of both japonica and indica cultivars.

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RFLP mapping of QTLs for yield and other related characters in rice

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Two F₂ populations were established from two indica/indica combinations: Tesanai 2/CB (TSA/CB) and Waiyin 2/CB (WY/CB). CB, from California, USA, was the common male parent. Tesanai 2, from Guangdong, China, is a high-yielding variety noted for its large panicles. Waiyin 2, from IRRI, has large grains. Seventy-three percent of 167 RFLP markers tested revealed polymorphisms between the parents of the two crosses. For each F₂ population, genotypes were determined for 171 plants with 93 RFLP markers in TSA/CB and 101 in WY/CB, respectively. Two linkage maps, made up of 89 marker loci and 93 marker loci of 12 linkage groups, were constructed, respectively, using Mapmaker (Lander et al 1987).

Each of eight characters were subjected to QTL mapping with both ANOVA (SAS Institute Inc. 1988) and interval mapping procedure (Lander and Botstein 1989). In TSA/CB, 22 QTLs for the eight characters were detected by one-way ANOVA (data not shown). The same QTLs were also detected by interval analysis (Table 1). In WY/CB, 19 QTLs for six traits were detected by one-way ANOVA, and, again,

Chromosomal locations of QTLs for length of shoot, root, coleoptile, and mesocotyl measured in slantboard tests in the Labelle/Black Gora and Labelle/Italica Livorno populations as determined by interval and single-factor analysis.

Chromosome no.	Vigor trait	Temp (°C)	Labelle/Black Gora		Labelle/Italica Livorno	
			% variance explained	Nearest marker	% variance explained	Nearest marker
1	Shoot	18, 25	7 ^a	RG536	-	-
	Root	18, 25	31 ^a	RG222	-	-
	Mesocotyl	25	13	RG811	-	-
2	Root	18	9	CDO718	-	-
	Shoot	18, 25	16 ^a	RZ452	18 ^b	OPAD13 ₇₂₀
3	Coleoptile	25	25	RZ448	-	-
	Mesocotyl	18, 25	10	RZ448	-	-
	Shoot	18	8 ^a	RG435	-	-
5	Root	18	-	-	11	OPAJ20 ₁₁₄₀
	Mesocotyl	25	13	RZ67	-	-
	Shoot	18	-	-	50	OPH19 ₁₃₄₀
6	Coleoptile	25	15 ^a	RG716	-	-
	Mesocotyl	18	-	-	14	OPX17 ₁₇₀₀
7	Root	18	-	-	16 ^a	OPY6 ₁₁₅₀
	Mesocotyl	18	-	-	13	RG678
	Shoot	25	28	RZ395	-	-
9	Shoot	18	10 ^a	RZ422	-	-
	Root	18	-	-	11 ^a	OPAA1 ₆₄₀
10	Root	18	-	-	14	OPX2 ₇₀₀
	Coleoptile	18	-	-	21	OPZ12 ₂₄₀₀
11	Coleoptile	18	-	-	13 ^a	OPAN15 ₁₀₅₀
	Mesocotyl	18	-	-	11 ^a	RZ536
12	Root	18	-	-	9 ^a	RG341

^aLabelle has the positive allele. ^bBy single-factor analysis.

Table 1. QTLs detected for yield components based on interval analysis (Mapmaker/QTL) in the Tesanai 2/CB F₂ population.

Trait ^a	QTL ^b	Interval	LOD ^c	% variation ^d explained	a ^e	d ^f	d/[a] ^g
GWT	gwt1	RG374-RG394	2.93	10.7	-1.96	12.36	6.32
	twt2	RG157-RG171	4.11	11.4	-9.14	7.10	0.78
	gwt4	RG143-RG214	3.10	8.7	-7.91	0.28	0.04
	gwt5	RG13-RG573	2.39	11.0	1.27	12.72	10.03
	gwt8	RZ66-RG598	2.31	7.8	-8.04	0.51	0.06
NP	np2	RG157-RG171	3.62	9.3	-1.39	2.27	1.64
	np4	RG143-RG214	9.68	26.1	-2.92	0.18	0.06
NG	ng1	RG374-RG394	4.41	17.2	-1.39	48.18	34.57
	ng2	RG25-RG157	2.79	9.0	-21.46	27.65	1.29
	ng8	RG978-RZ66	2.28	13.8	-30.55	9.49	0.31
	ng12	RG341-RG235	2.48	7.4	1.77	31.53	17.79
NS	ns3	RG104-RG348	2.32	6.8	-16.56	-45.87	-2.77
	ns8	RZ562-RG978	4.84	15.5	35.70	53.64	1.50
	ns12	RG457-RG341	2.34	7.4	-37.89	-9.61	-0.25
SF	sf1	RG374-RG394	3.86	12.2	-5.10	25.00	4.92
TGWT	tgwt1	RG173-RG532	3.01	12.6	1.63	-1.50	-0.92
	tgwt4	RG143-RG214	2.74	8.5	-1.39	0.55	0.39
	tgwt5	RG182-RG13	2.73	14.8	-1.55	-1.33	-0.86
SD	sd3	RG104-RG348	2.13	5.7	-5.43	-15.04	-2.77
	sd8	RZ562-RG978	3.73	10.9	11.79	14.69	1.25
	sd12	RG457-RG341	2.21	8.0	-14.06	-4.04	-0.29
NFB	nfb8	RG108-RZ562	6.49	20.9	1.91	-0.49	-0.25

^aGWT = grain weight plant⁻¹, NP = number of panicles plant⁻¹, NG = number of grams panicle⁻¹, NS = number of spikelets panicle⁻¹, SF = spikelet fertility, TGWT = 1000-grain weight, SD = spikelet density, NFB = number of first branches panicle⁻¹. ^bQTLs are named by trait abbreviations plus chromosomal number. ^cLog₁₀-likelihood. ^dPercent phenotypic variance explained. ^eAdditive gene effect at the putative QTL loci. ^fDominance effect at the putative QTL loci. ^gDegree of dominance.

Table 2. QTLs detected for yield components based on interval analysis (Mapmaker/QTL) in the Waiyin 2/CB F₂ population.

Trait ^a	QTL ^b	Interval	LOD ^c	% variation ^d explained	a ^e	d ^f	d/[a] ^g
GWT	gwt1	RG374-RG394	3.13	11.5	-6.70	-6.56	-0.98
	gwt4a	RG788-RG190	4.67	22.3	-8.85	-11.48	-1.30
	gwt5a	CD082-RG360	3.14	10.1	-8.59	-1.66	-0.19
NP	np2a	RG324A-RG324B	2.09	5.6	-1.06	1.13	1.06
	np5	RG360-RG9	2.86	9.9	-1.99	-0.24	-0.12
	np6	waxy-RG213	2.86	12.1	-1.51	-1.16	-0.76
TNS	tns6	RG138-RG64	5.01	13.1	-38.04	28.14	0.74
	tns8a	RG108-RZ562	2.27	7.3	10.79	43.50	4.03
	tns11	RG1094-RG118	4.38	12.5	-54.71	-43.41	-0.79
SF	sf1a	RG536-RG222	3.25	9.4	-8.27	-6.80	-0.82
	sf6	waxy-RG213	2.37	12.5	11.42	7.84	0.69
	sf8	RZ562-RZ617	2.25	6.7	-8.72	-0.51	-0.06
TGWT	tgwt1a	RZ649-RG381	2.12	5.8	1.23	1.10	0.90
	tgwt2	RG171-RG437	4.23	14.8	-2.42	0.57	0.24
	tgwt10	RG241-RG561	3.52	22.8	-2.89	1.32	0.46
SD	sd2	RG520-RG256	3.13	12.3	3.92	-21.09	-5.38
	sd6	RG138-RG64	5.15	13.3	-14.62	6.30	0.43
	sd8	RG108-RZ562	2.45	7.9	3.86	16.22	4.20
	sd11	RG103-RG2	2.31	6.3	-5.22	13.48	2.58

^{a-g}See Table 1 for definitions.

all 19 QTLs were detected by interval analysis (Table 2). These findings indicate that both statistical procedures produce very similar results.

The QTLs identified are named with trait abbreviation followed by chromosomal number (Tables 1 and 2). QTLs controlling grain weight plant⁻¹ (GWT) were located within five intervals (gwt1, gwt2, gwt4, gwt5, and gwt8) in TSA/CB. The five QTLs for GWT are located on chromosomes 1, 2, 4, 5 and 8, with one in each chromosome (Table 1). In WY/CB, however, only 3 intervals containing QTLs (gwt1, gwt4a, and gwt5a) controlling GWT were detected. Three QTLs for GWT are located on each of chromosomes 1.4, and 5 (Table 2).

Among the 41 QTLs for various traits detected in both populations. 23 QTLs can explain phenotypic variance larger than 10%. Some of the QTLs, such as np4, gwt4a, tgwt10, and nfb8, explained more than 20% of variance (Tables 1 and 2). If a QTL can explain larger variation and is significantly different from other QTLs (e.g., much larger LOD score), it can be assumed that this would be a major gene—not a QTL. QTL np4 (Table 1) from TSA seems to have such characteristics. Number of panicles (NP) is generally considered to be under the control of both major and minor genes. QTL np4 might be a major gene that joins other QTLs with lesser effects, such as np2, to control panicle development.

In general, 1 to 3 QTLs were detected for each trait in both populations (Tables 1 and 2). Comparison of QTLs for individual traits showed that a majority of QTLs are present in only one of the two populations. For example, three QTLs were detected for total number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ (NS) but only one (tns8) was detected in both populations.

Performance of female parents is very different, and a different set of operating genes is likely to control it.

Altogether, we found three QTLs (gwt1, tns8, sd8) shared by both populations. Different QTLs detected in different populations provide an opportunity to combine them to produce new breeding lines with higher yield potential. As DNA markers are not subject to environmental effects, marker-aided selection of the QTLs

can be conducted in early generations of breeding programs. QTL mapping of rice yield and related characters is the first step to apply marker technology to breeding programs for improving yield potential.

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Use of DNA markers in constructing multilines

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Construction of multilines, each with a major resistance gene(s) for different Korean blast races, is under way to characterize resistance genes and to test whether deployment of multiple resistance genes in this fashion will provide durable resistance to blast disease. Resistance genes were introgressed from different donors into the commercial cultivars. Identifying molecular markers linked to these genes is essential to speed up the process of making the multilines.

Three isolines (BC₅F₃) constructed using Daeseongbyeo as a donor and Chucheongbyeo as the recurrent parent were used in the gene-tagging experiment. Each line shows resistance to blast isolates KJ-201, KJ-301, and KI-313, respectively (see table). These three isolates were used individually for inoculation during near-isogenic line (NIL) development. Genetic analysis of Daeseongbyeo indicated that

Autoradiograph showing hybridization pattern of RG213 in Daeseongbyeo (D), pooled three isolines (I), and Chucheongbyeo (R) DNA digested with the following enzymes: *Bam*HI (1), *Eco*RI (2), *Eco*RV (3) *Sca*I (4), and *Hind*III (5). The isolate resistant to race KJ-201 only showed the same restriction pattern as the donor with *Sca*I.

Reaction^a of differential varieties and parents to four races of rice blast fungus.

Variety	Race			
	KJ-101	KJ-201	KJ-301	KI-313
<i>Differential variety</i>				
Tetep	R	R	R	R
Tongil	R	R	R	S
Nongbaeg	S	S	R	R
Jinheung	S	S	S	S
<i>Parents</i>				
Daeseongbyeo	S	R	R	R
Chucheongbyeo	S	S	S	S

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.

one dominant gene conditions resistance to isolates KJ-201 and KI-313 and two dominant genes condition resistance to KJ-301 (Kim 1994).

Fifteen RFLP markers previously reported to be linked to major blast resistance genes in different rice germplasm (McCouch et al 1993) and six microsatellite markers mapped to nearby regions were surveyed for polymorphism among the lines. One restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) marker, RG213, on chromosome 6 showed polymorphism between the isogenic lines (see figure).

Using the segregating populations, this marker is being tested to determine whether it is linked to the resistance gene (KJ-201).

We also have used random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) technique to identify primers that amplify DNA that is polymorphic between the NILs. Three hundred RAPD primers were used to analyze the genome. Each primer amplified 3.1 loci on average (corresponding to about 930 loci). This survey revealed one locus putatively linked to resistance and demonstrated that the lines were nearly isogenic to their recurrent parent, Chucheongbyeo. This marker also is being tested.

Other sets of NILs were developed using two recurrent parents and four donor parents. Based on their reaction to races and phenotype, six NILs were selected and subjected to yield trials and hot-spot leaf blast nursery test. The reaction degree of six NILs appeared to be less severe than that of their respective recurrent parent.

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